

Case Report

“Personalizing” commonly used drugs: A challenging case of 5-Fluorouracil dosing

Rujuta P. Saksena^{1*} and Rebecca A. Moss^{2*}

¹Division of Medical Oncology, Rutgers Cancer Institute of New Jersey

²Rutgers Cancer Institute of New Jersey, 195 Little Albany Street, New Brunswick, NJ 08903

* Corresponding authors, Rebecca A. Moss, Email: mossr1@cinj.rutgers.edu; Rujuta P. Saksena, rujuta.patel@gmail.com

Introduction

Fluorouracil (5-FU) is commonly used in the clinic despite individual pharmacokinetic (PK) variation that can result in unpredictable toxicity and variable antineoplastic effects. Therapeutic drug monitoring (TDM) of 5-FU is commercially available and can be of utility in routine clinical practice. Pharmacokinetic assays can be used to “personalize” 5-FU administration, which would translate to more efficacy and less toxicity for the individual.

Monitoring 5-FU plasma levels in combination regimens, such as FOLFOX and FOLFIRI, would provide a rational approach for identifying the toxicity-inducing component of the regimen and allow specific dose adjustment of 5-FU without modifying the doses of other cytotoxic agents.

As genetic polymorphisms can have a significant impact on 5-FU metabolism, it is important to identify these factors to permit the tailoring of treatment.

In this report, we describe a 59 year old man who had significant toxicity to 5-FU prescribed in the adjuvant setting for stage III colon cancer but was able to complete a six month course of therapy with both genotype testing and the use of PK-based 5-FU dosing to optimize his treatment effectively and safely.

Case Report

During his first surveillance colonoscopy, a 59 year old man was found to have a high-grade dysplastic lesion. He underwent a segmental colonic resection and was diagnosed with stage III colon adenocarcinoma, pathologic staging T2N1. At an outside institution, he was started on adjuvant chemotherapy with an unusual regimen consisting of both bolus 5-FU and capecitabine: he received oxaliplatin 85 mg/m² on day 1, bolus 5-FU 400 mg/m² with leucovorin (LV) 200 mg/m² on day 1, as well as capecitabine 1000 mg/m² twice daily on days 1 through 7 every 2 weeks. After two cycles of this regimen, he was hospitalized with severe vomiting, diarrhea, hypotension, mucositis, renal failure, and pancytopenia. Given a constellation of symptoms consistent with 5-FU toxicity, he was given a clinical diagnosis of dihydropyrimidine dehydrogenase (DPD) deficiency, but no genetic testing was performed.

He then transferred his care to our institution.

Our clinical impression was that the proximity of

the sequential dosing of 5-FU, LV, and capecitabine could explain the toxicity in the absence of any metabolic deficiency, as there is reported increased toxicity when capecitabine is given after 5-FU/LV.[1] Genotype testing revealed that DPYD (the gene that encodes dihydropyrimidine dehydrogenase or DPD) was normal at six sites tested, predicting normal DPD activity. However, the patient was found to be homozygous for TYMS (*thymidylate synthase gene*) 6bp deletion, which is associated with reduced thymidylate synthase (TS) expression and increased 5-FU sensitivity,[2,3] and he was heterozygous for the MTHFR mutation.

Based on his genotype, we expected this patient to have slightly increased sensitivity to 5-FU. With the goal of treating him with curative intent for his node positive colon cancer, we resumed adjuvant chemotherapy with a dose-escalation approach and close monitoring of 5-FU plasma levels. He was started on FOLFOX4 with 50% reduced dose infusional 5-FU without bolus. We monitored his plasma 5-FU levels with every cycle using the OnDose immunoassay (provided by Myriad Genetics). His dose was gradually titrated upwards to goal level of AUC 20-25 mg-h/L. He was subsequently able to tolerate bolus 5FU/LV prior to his 5-FU infusions.

With close monitoring of his plasma drug levels, he did not have any further toxicity and completed a full six months of adjuvant chemotherapy uneventfully.

He had no evidence of recurrent disease on routine follow up one year postoperatively.

Discussion

Highlights:

1. Utility of pharmacokinetically based 5-FU dosing
2. Importance of genotype testing for 5-FU metabolism
3. Toxicity when switching from 5-FU/LV to capecitabine

5-Fluorouracil (5-FU) is the cornerstone of colorectal cancer treatment, used in both the adjuvant and metastatic settings. Traditionally, 5-FU dosing is based on body surface area (BSA, mg/m²).

Unfortunately, BSA based dosing is associated with considerable variability in plasma 5-FU levels.

Several studies have demonstrated the lack of association between BSA and 5-FU exposure. [4-7] In fact, with BSA-based 5-FU dosing, we can expect only 20%–30% of patients to have

therapeutic drug levels.[8] Approximately 40%–60% of patients are underdosed, putting them at risk for treatment failure and negative clinical outcomes (especially in the adjuvant setting). In the 10%–20% of patients that are overdosed, toxicity remains a major concern. 5-FU toxicity can manifest as gastrointestinal symptoms, myelosuppression, neurological symptoms, or ischemic heart disease. In general, there is a 10-15% risk of gastrointestinal and hematologic toxicity with 5-FU.[9] To avoid serious toxicity or compromised efficacy, it is crucial that we optimize 5-FU dosing.

The dosing of 5-FU is challenging due to its narrow therapeutic index and also its significant pharmacokinetic variability.[10] Reasons for this pharmacokinetic variation include genetic differences in drug metabolism, performance status, age, sex, weight, mode and schedule of drug administration, diet, and interactions with other medications.[7,11-14]

It is clear that BSA-based 5-FU dosing is suboptimal. A more effective approach is the use of pharmacokinetically (PK) based assays for TDM.

Many studies have established a strong correlation between 5-FU plasma levels and the biological effects of 5-FU, where the use of PK-based dosing reflects improved outcomes and reduced toxicity.[15-25] The biological effects of 5-FU are most closely associated with total drug exposure or area under the curve (AUC). These studies have identified an optimal therapeutic range for 5-FU using AUC.[15,16,26-29] Despite different administration modes, varying schedules, and diverse combination regimens of 5-FU, a therapeutic dose range of AUC 20–25 mg•hr/L has been shown to yield positive results with PK-based assays.[15,16,30]

Gamelin et al. have conducted several studies looking at this concept. For example, they conducted a randomized, phase III trial using an infusion regimen of 5-FU/LV to compare standard BSA dosing with TDM in metastatic colorectal cancer.[27] In the PK arm, patients were dosed based on BSA in the first cycle with subsequent doses adjusted to a target AUC of 20–24 mg•h/L based on drug levels determined by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) monitoring in the previous cycle. Most patients (85% of those assigned to the dose-adjusted group) did not receive an optimal dose of 5-FU. On average, four cycles of therapy were required to achieve the target concentration.

However, the therapeutic range for 5-FU was eventually achieved in 94% of patients. In terms of safety, the overall incidence of grade 3–4 toxicity was substantially reduced in patients receiving PK guided 5-FU (4%) compared with BSA dosed 5-FU (18%). With respect to clinical efficacy, patients in the PK arm had an overall response rate of 34%, which was twofold higher than the 18% response rate seen in the BSA arm. An improvement in median overall survival was observed from 16 months for the BSA dosed patients to 22 months for the PK guided group.[27] With a median follow up of 3 years, this study demonstrated that individualized 5-FU dosing

not only improved efficacy and safety, but was also easily applicable in clinical practice.

Historically, liquid chromatography and mass spectroscopy based tests have been available only at specialized facilities. A commercially available nanoparticle antibody-based immunoassay for 5-FU measurement such as was used for our patient allows for routine monitoring of 5-FU in clinical practice.

TDM is certainly feasible in routine practice and can likely be applied to all patients being treated with 5-FU. However, in a select group of patients, it might also be important to identify genetic factors that could affect 5-FU metabolism. Genetic alterations in DPD, TS, or Methylenetetrahydrofolate reductase (MTHFR) can influence 5-FU metabolism.

DPD (encoded by the *DPYD* gene) is a key enzyme in 5-FU catabolism and degrades over 80% of 5-FU.

Reduced DPD activity can result in accumulation of active 5-FU metabolite (FdUMP), leading to toxicity. Partial DPD deficiency has been observed in 3%–5% of the general population, while complete deficiency is rare (0.1%).[10] However, almost half of the patients who experience 5-FU toxicity have no known DPD deficiency, indicating the presence of other contributing factors. TS, encoded by the *TYMS* gene, is the primary target of 5-FU. *TYMS* mutations result in reduced expression of TS and may be associated with higher responsiveness to 5-FU therapy and possible increased risk of toxicity.[2,3] *MTHFR* mutations lead to reduced *MTHFR* enzyme activity, which increases intracellular folate metabolites and may increase the activity rate of TS. The effect of an *MTHFR* mutation on 5-FU efficacy and toxicity is unclear though. In general, genotype information should be interpreted within the clinical context. To avoid toxicity in patients with these mutations, one has to consider TDM, 5-FU dose modification, increased surveillance, and/or alternative chemotherapy.

Although our patient had normal DPD activity, he had three separate polymorphisms in genes involved in 5-FU metabolism, which may have increased his sensitivity to 5-FU. However, he had also received an unconventional dose of capecitabine immediately following bolus 5-FU and LV, which has been shown to increase toxicity significantly. Hennig et al found that there was excess sequence-specific toxicity in those receiving FU/LV first followed by capecitabine (79% of patients in this group had grade 3 or > toxicity, compared with 28% receiving capecitabine as the first treatment).[1] Oncologists should be aware of this sequence-specific risk if considering crossing patients over from FU/LV to capecitabine-based regimens. In this case, it was uncertain whether his genetic abnormalities contributed to 5-FU toxicity or whether it was a result of the initial chemotherapy regimen that he received.

This case highlights the importance of 5-FU monitoring in clinical practice. In our quest for personalized medicine and desire to individualize treatment for patients, starting with “customizing” commonly used drugs, such as 5FU, is a sensible strategy to improve patient care and outcomes.

References

1. Hennig IM, Naik JD, Brown S, Szubert A, Anthony DA, *et al.* (2008). Severe sequence-specific toxicity when capecitabine is given after fluorouracil and leucovorin. *J Clin Oncol*, 26(20): 3411-3417.
2. Marsh S, McKay JA, Cassidy J, McLeod HL (2001). Polymorphism in the thymidylate synthase promoter enhancer region in colorectal cancer. *Int J Oncol*, 19(2): 383-386.
3. Pullarkat ST, Stoehlmacher J, Ghaderi V, Xiong YP, Ingles SA, *et al.* (2001). Thymidylate synthase gene polymorphism determines response and toxicity of 5-FU chemotherapy. *Pharmacogenomics J*, 1(1): 65-70.
4. Milano G, Etienne MC, Cassuto-Viguier E, Thyss A, Santini J, *et al.* (1992). Influence of sex and age on fluorouracil clearance. *J Clin Oncol*, 10(7): 1171-1175.
5. Gamelin E, Boisdrion-Celle M, Guerin-Meyer V, Delva R, Lortholary A, *et al.* (1999). Correlation between uracil and dihydrouracil plasma ratio, fluorouracil (5-FU) pharmacokinetic parameters, and tolerance in patients with advanced colorectal cancer: A potential interest for predicting 5-FU toxicity and determining optimal 5-FU dosage. *J Clin Oncol*, 17(4): 1105.
6. Fety R, Rolland F, Barberi-Heyob M, Hardouin A, Campion L, *et al.* (1998). Clinical impact of pharmacokinetically-guided dose adaptation of 5-fluorouracil: results from a multicentric randomized trial in patients with locally advanced head and neck carcinomas. *Clin Cancer Res*, 4(9): 2039-2045.
7. Undevia SD, Gomez-Abuin G, Ratain MJ (2005). Pharmacokinetic variability of anticancer agents. *Nat Rev Cancer*, 5(6): 447-458.
8. Saif MW, Choma A, Salamone SJ, Chu E (2009). Pharmacokinetically guided dose adjustment of 5-fluorouracil: a rational approach to improving therapeutic outcomes. *J Natl Cancer Inst*, 101(22): 1543-1552.
9. Hu CY, Chan W, Delclos GP, Du XL (2012). Adjuvant chemotherapy and risk of gastrointestinal, hematologic, and cardiac toxicities in elderly patients with stage III colon cancer. *Am J Clin Oncol*, 35(3): 228-236.
10. Ploylearmsaeng SA, Fuhr U, Jetter A (2006). How may anticancer chemotherapy with fluorouracil be individualised? *Clin Pharmacokinet*, 45(6): 567-592.
11. de Jonge ME, Huitema AD, Schellens JH, Rodenhuis S, Beijnen JH (2005). Individualised cancer chemotherapy: strategies and performance of prospective studies on therapeutic drug monitoring with dose adaptation: a review. *Clinical pharmacokinetics*, 44(2):147-173.
12. Hon YY, Evans WE (1998). Making TDM work to optimize cancer chemotherapy: a multidisciplinary team approach. *Clin Chem*, 44(2): 388-400.
13. Krynetski EY, Evans WE (1998). Pharmacogenetics of cancer therapy: getting personal. *Am J Hum Genet*, 63(1): 11-16.
14. Partridge AH, Avorn J, Wang PS, Winer EP (2002). Adherence to therapy with oral antineoplastic agents. *J Natl Cancer Inst*, 94(9): 652-661.
15. Gamelin EC, Danquechin-Dorval EM, Dumesnil YF, *et al.* (1996). Relationship between 5-fluorouracil (5-FU) dose intensity and therapeutic response in patients with advanced colorectal cancer receiving infusional therapy containing 5-FU. *Cancer*, 77(3):441-451.
16. Gamelin E, Boisdrion-Celle M, Delva R, Regimbeau C, Cailleux PE, *et al.* (1998). Long-term weekly treatment of colorectal metastatic cancer with fluorouracil and leucovorin: results of a multicentric prospective trial of fluorouracil dosage optimization by pharmacokinetic monitoring in 152 patients. *J Clin Oncol*, 16(4): 1470-1478.
17. Thyss A, Milano G, Renee N, Vallicioni J, Schneider M, *et al.* (1986). Clinical pharmacokinetic study of 5-FU in continuous 5-day infusions for head and neck cancer. *Cancer Chemother Pharmacol*, 16(1): 64-66.
18. Santini J, Milano G, Thyss A, Renee N, Viens P, *et al.* (1989). 5-FU therapeutic monitoring with dose adjustment leads to an improved therapeutic index in head and neck cancer. *Br J Cancer*, 59(2): 287-290.
19. Au JL, Rustum YM, Ledesma EJ, Mittelman A, Creaven PJ (1982). Clinical pharmacological studies of concurrent infusion of 5-fluorouracil and thymidine in treatment of colorectal carcinomas. *Cancer Res*, 42(7): 2930-2937.
20. Hillcoat BL, McCulloch PB, Figueredo AT, Ehsan MH, Rosenfeld JM (1978). Clinical response and plasma levels of 5-fluorouracil in patients with colonic cancer treated by drug infusion. *Br J Cancer*, 38(6): 719-724.
21. Kirkwood JM, Ensminger W, Rosowsky A, Papathanasopoulos N, Frei E rd (1980). Comparison of pharmacokinetics of 5-fluorouracil and 5-fluorouracil with concurrent thymidine infusions in a Phase I trial. *Cancer Res*, 40(1): 107-113.
22. Trump DL, Egorin MJ, Forrest A, Willson JK, Remick S, *et al.* (1991). Pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic analysis of fluorouracil during 72-hour continuous infusion with and without dipyrindamole. *J Clin Oncol*, 9(11): 2027-2035.
23. van Groeningen CJ, Pinedo HM, Heddes J, Kok RM, de Jong AP, *et al.* (1988). Pharmacokinetics of 5-fluorouracil assessed with a sensitive mass spectrometric method in patients on a dose escalation schedule. *Cancer Res*, 48(23): 6956-6961.
24. Yoshida T, Araki E, Iigo M, Fujii T, Yoshino M, *et al.* (1990). Clinical significance of monitoring serum levels of 5-fluorouracil by continuous infusion in patients with advanced colonic cancer. *Cancer Chemother Pharmacol*, 26(5): 352-354.
25. Jodrell DI, Stewart M, Aird R, Knowles G, Bowman A, *et al.* (2001). 5-fluorouracil steady state pharmacokinetics and outcome in patients receiving protracted venous infusion for advanced colorectal cancer. *Br J Cancer*, 84(5): 600-603.
26. Gamelin E, Boisdrion-Celle M (1999). Dose monitoring of 5-fluorouracil in patients with colorectal or head and neck cancer—status of the art. *Crit Rev Oncol Hematol*, 30(1): 71-79.
27. Gamelin E, Delva R, Jacob J, *et al.* (2008). Individual fluorouracil dose adjustment based on pharmacokinetic follow-up compared with conventional dosage: results of a multicenter randomized trial of patients with metastatic colorectal cancer. *J Clin Oncol*, 26(13):2099-2105.
28. Ychou M, Duffour J, Kramar A, *et al.* (2003). Individual 5-FU dose adaptation in metastatic colorectal cancer: results of a phase II study using a bimonthly pharmacokinetically intensified LV5FU2 regimen. *Cancer chemotherapy and pharmacology*, 52(4):282-290.
29. Ychou M, Duffour J, Pinguet F, *et al.* (1999). Individual 5FU-dose adaptation schedule using bimonthly pharmacokinetically modulated LV5FU2 regimen: a feasibility study in patients with advanced colorectal cancer. *Anticancer research*, 19(3B):2229-2235.
30. Milano G, Roman P, Khater R, Frenay M, Renee N, *et al.* (1988). Dose versus pharmacokinetics for predicting tolerance to 5-day continuous infusion of 5-FU. *Int J Cancer*, 41(4): 537-541.